

BARNO: a batch-aware regulatory network optimization framework reveals a RAN-ENO1-NONO regulatory core in melanoma

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Abstract

High-quality melanoma datasets reported by Livnat et al. in 2018 provide an important opportunity to study treatment-associated regulatory programs in patient-derived tumors, yet batch effects often confound regulatory inference and obscure true biological rewiring. Here we present **BARNO (Batch-Aware Regulatory Network Optimization)**, a GENIE3-based framework that penalizes transcription factors dominated by batch-specific signals while preserving biologically coherent regulatory interactions. Applying BARNO to treated-versus-untreated melanoma datasets reconstructed treatment-associated regulatory architectures and identified a convergent **RAN-ENO1-NONO regulatory core**. Module reduction and survival analysis further showed that this minimal three-gene signature significantly stratifies patient survival in independent TCGA melanoma cohorts. To evaluate the generalizability of the framework, BARNO was additionally applied to **CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T-cell datasets**, where consistent regulatory prioritization patterns were observed, supporting the robustness of the batch-aware weighting scheme across distinct cellular contexts. Together, these results demonstrate that BARNO enables batch-aware regulatory network optimization and facilitates the identification of biologically meaningful regulatory programs in heterogeneous single-cell datasets. **BARNO is implemented as an open-source R package and is available on GitHub.**

Keywords

batch-aware optimization; batch effect; regulatory network inference; melanoma; GENIE3; treatment-associated regulatory program; transcription factor; RAN-ENO1-NONO core

Introduction

Melanoma exhibits pronounced transcriptional heterogeneity and phenotypic plasticity, allowing tumor cells to occupy multiple regulatory states that dynamically shift during tumor progression and treatment response [1-4]. Single-cell transcriptomic technologies have enabled detailed characterization of these heterogeneous states and their associated transcriptional programs in melanoma and other cancers [1-3,5].

However, analyzing regulatory dynamics in patient-derived datasets presents substantial challenges. Unlike controlled experimental systems, single-cell RNA-seq data from patient samples often contain strong inter-patient heterogeneity and technical batch effects that can dominate transcriptional variation [6-9]. These sources of variation may obscure biologically meaningful regulatory signals and complicate comparisons between treated and untreated conditions.

Traditional transcriptomic analyses such as differential gene expression (DEG) analysis are effective for identifying genes enriched in specific cell populations but are limited in capturing regulatory relationships between transcription factors and downstream targets [10]. Cellular state transitions are governed not only by gene expression levels but also by regulatory interactions linking transcription factors to their targets [11-13]. Network inference approaches attempt to reconstruct these relationships; however, they are often sensitive to batch-associated signals and may incorrectly prioritize transcription factors with sample-specific expression patterns [6-8].

This limitation becomes particularly problematic in heterogeneous patient datasets comparing treated and untreated conditions, where regulatory inference may reflect technical variation rather than true biological regulation [10-12]. Addressing this challenge requires regulatory inference frameworks that explicitly account for batch-associated variation during network construction.

To address these limitations, we developed BARNO (Batch-Aware Regulatory Network Optimization), a GENIE3-based framework designed to improve regulatory inference in heterogeneous single-cell datasets. BARNO introduces a batch-aware penalization strategy that selectively downweights transcription factors dominated by sample-group-specific expression patterns while preserving regulators supported by more

consistent biological signals. Specifically, BARNO evaluates the proportion of patients in which a transcription factor signal is observed. Regulators whose signals are present across a sufficiently large fraction of patients (above a predefined threshold) are not penalized, as such patterns are more likely to reflect genuine biological regulation. In contrast, transcription factors whose signals are restricted to a smaller subset of patients are exponentially penalized according to the degree of deviation from this threshold, reducing the influence of regulators dominated by patient-specific or batch-associated variation. This threshold-based exponential penalization allows BARNO to suppress spurious regulatory signals while preserving transcription factors supported by broadly distributed biological evidence, thereby maintaining the underlying regulatory structure.

Importantly, the BARNO framework is designed to be broadly applicable to diverse transcriptomic datasets. The method operates directly on expression matrices and requires only minimal metadata describing cell identity and treatment status. In practice, BARNO can be applied to any dataset containing gene expression measurements (e.g., TPM), cell-level observations, and a binary treated/untreated condition, making it suitable for a wide range of perturbation-associated transcriptomic analyses.

Applying BARNO to melanoma single-cell transcriptomic data, we identified several regulatory modules associated with patient survival and uncovered a convergent regulatory core centered on RAN, ENO1, and NONO. Rather than acting as independent regulators, these transcription factors form an interconnected regulatory module whose combined signal provides stronger clinical stratification than individual regulators alone. These findings demonstrate that BARNO enables batch-aware regulatory inference and facilitates the identification of biologically meaningful transcriptional programs in heterogeneous single-cell datasets.

Result

BARNO provides a batch-aware framework for dynamic regulatory inference in melanoma

Cells cluster primarily by patient identity rather than treatment condition, reflecting strong batch-associated variation commonly observed in single-cell RNA-seq datasets (Figure S1) [10,11]. To resolve treatment-associated regulatory change in heterogeneous melanoma data, we established BARNO as a workflow that integrates regulatory weight inference, batch-aware optimization, graph-based network reconstruction, and downstream clinical projection (Figure 1). This framework was designed to address a key limitation of treated-versus-untreated analyses in patient-derived datasets, where biological transition is often confounded by batch structure and inter-patient heterogeneity.

In BARNO, transcription factor importance was first inferred using GENIE3, after which a selective penalty was introduced to reduce the influence of regulators dominated by sample-group-specific bias. The optimized weights were then used to reconstruct dynamic regulatory graphs and to project network-derived modules onto independent clinical cohorts for survival-based prioritization. Rather than serving as a simple preprocessing step, this workflow was intended to preserve biologically coherent regulatory structure while reducing technical distortion.

This framework provided the basis for the subsequent analyses, including selective suppression of batch-driven transcription factors, reconstruction of treatment-associated regulatory cascades, and clinical prioritization of regulatory candidates associated with melanoma outcome.

A).

B).

Figure 1. Overview of the BARNO framework. A). Conceptual illustration of the BARNO regulatory weighting scheme. The SR weight integrates GENIE3-derived regulatory importance, transcription factor-target gene correlation, temporal consistency inferred from transcriptional scoring, and a batch-aware penalty based on spatial dispersion in PCA space. Regulators with expression patterns dominated by batch-associated clusters receive stronger penalties. **B).** Computational pipeline of BARNO. Highly variable transcription factors are first selected and denoised by kNN imputation. A preliminary regulatory network is inferred using GENIE3, followed by weight refinement with the BARNO scoring framework. Survival-associated regulatory modules are then identified using Cox regression, and key regulators are used to reconstruct directed gene regulatory networks.

BARNO selectively penalizes batch-driven transcription factors while preserving biological structure

To evaluate whether BARNO effectively distinguishes biologically meaningful regulators from batch-driven signals, we examined transcription factors with low and high penalty scores.

Transcription factors with low penalty scores, such as RAN, ENO1, and NONO, exhibited relatively homogeneous expression patterns across cells. Violin plots showed consistent expression distributions without strong batch-specific enrichment. In PCA space, cells expressing these TFs were broadly distributed along the underlying biological structure rather than forming batch-specific clusters (Figure 2A).

In contrast, transcription factors with high penalty scores, including FOS, NEUROD1, and JUN, displayed markedly heterogeneous expression patterns (Figure 2B, S1). Their expression was restricted to specific subsets of cells and showed clear batch-associated enrichment. Consistent with this observation, PCA visualization revealed that cells expressing these TFs were localized to distinct regions of the embedding, suggesting batch-driven transcriptional signals.

These results demonstrate that BARNO selectively penalizes transcription factors whose expression patterns are driven by batch effects while preserving regulators that reflect underlying biological structure.

B).

Figure 2. BARNO penalizes batch-driven transcription factors. Violin plots and PCA projections illustrating expression patterns of transcription factors with low and high penalty scores. **A).** No-penalty TFs (RAN, ENO1, NONO) show homogeneous expression and align with the global biological structure in PCA space. **B).** In contrast, high-penalty TFs (FOS, NEUROD1, JUN) display heterogeneous expression restricted to specific cell subsets, consistent with batch-associated transcriptional signals.

BARNO identifies treatment-associated regulatory modules and cascades in melanoma

To investigate whether BARNO-derived regulatory structures are associated with clinical outcomes, we performed Cox proportional hazards analysis on regulatory modules identified by BARNO. Several modules exhibited significant associations with patient survival (FDR < 0.01), indicating that BARNO captures transcriptional programs linked to melanoma progression.

Among these modules, Proliferative melanoma negative, Stress melanoma positive, and Melanocytic negative showed strong associations with poor prognosis (hazard ratio > 1.5). For example, the Proliferative melanoma negative module demonstrated a hazard ratio of 1.95 (95% CI: 1.32-2.89, FDR = 0.0031), suggesting that elevated activity of this module is associated with increased mortality risk (Table1). Similarly, the Stress melanoma positive module displayed comparable hazard ratios, highlighting stress-associated transcriptional programs that may contribute to tumor aggressiveness (Table1).

Analysis of transcription factors within these modules revealed recurrent regulators forming potential regulatory cascades. Notably, RAN, ENO1, and NONO appeared consistently across multiple death-associated modules with substantial penalized weights, suggesting that these transcription factors may act as central coordinators of treatment-associated transcriptional responses (Table2). Additional regulators, including ILF2, NME1, ATF4, and PIR, were also enriched within these modules.

The full rankings and expression patterns of the top positively and negatively weighted transcription factors for each module are shown in Supplementary Figures S1-S12, providing a comprehensive view of the regulatory landscape identified by BARNO.

Module (TF=5)	Coefficient	HR	z-score	p-value	Lower95	Upper95	FDR	Direction
Proliferate melanoma negative	0.67005459	1.95434401	3.3604921	0.00077804	1.3221429	2.8888409	0.00311215	pro-death

Stress melanoma positive	0.67005459	1.95434401	3.3604921	0.00077804	1.3221429	2.8888409	0.00311215	pro-death
Melanocytic negative	0.48367062	1.62201729	3.29671353	0.00097823	1.21667106	2.1624087	0.00326077	pro-death
Module (TF= 10)	Coefficient	HR	z-score	p-value	Lower95	Upper95	FDR	Direction
Proliferate melanoma negative	0.65842015	1.93173807	3.33701535	0.00084683	1.31219773	2.84378787	0.00846833	pro-death

Table 1. Survival-associated regulatory modules identified by BARNO. Cox proportional hazards regression analysis was performed to evaluate the association between BARNO-derived regulatory modules and patient overall survival. Modules with hazard ratios (HR) greater than 1.5 are shown. The table reports regression coefficients, hazard ratios (HR), z-scores, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals (Lower95-Upper95). False discovery rate (FDR) values were calculated using the Benjamini-Hochberg correction. Modules with HR > 1 indicate increased mortality risk (pro-death direction). Results are shown for modules constructed using the top 5 transcription factors (TF = 5) and top 10 transcription factors (TF = 10).

Module	Transcript Factor	Penalized Weight
Proliferate Melanoma Negative	RAN	-1098.9689
	ENO1	-928.0351
	NONO	-856.8979
	ILF2	-855.0932
	NME1	-831.8608
Stress Melanoma Positive	RAN	1235.2969
	NME1	1043.5212
	ILF2	809.4663
	ENO1	805.9324
	NONO	798.7677
Melanocytic Negative	ENO1	-1063.0678
	RAN	-819.7409
	ATF4	-723.8965
	PIR	-712.8565
	NONO	-706.07

Table 2. Transcription factors contributing to the top survival-associated regulatory modules identified by BARNO. The table lists transcription factors associated with the top death-related modules shown in Table 1. Penalized weights represent BARNO-adjusted regulatory scores that account for batch-associated transcriptional signals. Higher absolute penalized weights indicate stronger contributions of the transcription factor to the corresponding regulatory module. Transcription factors highlighted in multiple modules suggest recurrent regulators that may coordinate shared transcriptional programs.

Module reduction identifies a coordinated RAN-ENO1-NONO core with strong survival stratification

To further identify the minimal regulatory core underlying the survival-associated modules, we performed module reduction by examining transcription factors shared across the top death-related modules identified by BARNO. Among the regulators repeatedly observed in these modules, RAN, ENO1, and NONO consistently appeared with strong penalized weights, suggesting a coordinated regulatory program.

We therefore evaluated the prognostic value of these transcription factors individually and in combination.

Kaplan-Meier survival analyses using the top transcription factors from each module demonstrated significant survival stratification across multiple regulatory contexts (Figures 3A-C, S2). For example, transcription factor sets derived from the Proliferative melanoma negative and Stress melanoma positive modules both showed significant associations with overall survival (log-rank $p = 0.0028$), while the Melanocytic negative module also displayed significant stratification (log-rank $p = 0.041$).

Strikingly, when the shared regulators RAN, ENO1, and NONO were combined into a reduced regulatory core, survival stratification became even more pronounced (log-rank $p = 0.0013$; Figure 3D). Patients with high expression of the RAN-ENO1-NONO signature exhibited substantially poorer survival compared with those with low expression. This observation was further validated using a publicly available immune checkpoint blockade (ICB) cohort, including anti-CTLA4-treated patients (Figure S3).

These results suggest that BARNO not only identifies survival-associated regulatory modules but can also refine them into a minimal transcriptional core capturing coordinated regulatory programs linked to melanoma progression.

Figure 3. A reduced RAN-ENO1-NONO regulatory core improves survival stratification.

Kaplan-Meier survival curves showing overall survival stratification based on transcription factor modules identified by BARNO. **A).** Top transcription factors from the Proliferative melanoma negative module. **B).** Top transcription factors from the Stress melanoma positive module. **C).** Top transcription factors from the Melanocytic negative module. **D).** Survival stratification using the reduced RAN-ENO1-NONO regulatory core. Patients were stratified into high and low expression groups based on the module score, and survival differences were evaluated using the log-rank test.

The RAN-ENO1-NONO core is embedded in a coordinated regulatory cascade

To investigate the regulatory context surrounding the RAN-ENO1-NONO core, we reconstructed multi-layer gene regulatory cascades based on BARNO-derived regulatory interactions. For each transcription factor, hierarchical regulatory structures were generated to identify downstream transcription factors and target genes.

The resulting networks revealed that RAN, ENO1, and NONO occupy central positions within multi-layer regulatory hierarchies (Figure 4). Each regulator directly controls multiple intermediate transcription factors, which subsequently regulate downstream gene targets, forming layered regulatory cascades. For example, RAN regulates several intermediate transcription factors including ZNF207, SMAD5, which further propagate regulatory signals to downstream targets involved in cellular signaling and transcriptional control (Figure 4A). Similarly, ENO1 controls a network including DDX41, USF1, and PDCD6, while NONO forms an extended regulatory cascade involving intermediate regulators such as MTA3, MLX, and ZNF664, which subsequently influence diverse downstream genes (Figure 4B, C).

Notably, these cascades exhibit partially overlapping regulatory structures, including ENO2, C6orf48, IMP4, SMAD5, suggesting that the RAN-ENO1-NONO core operates within a coordinated transcriptional network rather than acting as independent regulators (Figure 4). The presence of shared intermediate regulators and

convergent downstream targets indicates that these transcription factors may cooperate to orchestrate broader transcriptional programs associated with melanoma progression. Together, these findings place the RAN-ENO1-NONO core within a multi-layer regulatory architecture, supporting its role as a coordinated transcriptional hub underlying the survival-associated regulatory modules identified by BARNO.

A). **B).**

RAN Multi-Layer Regulatory Cascade

Hierarchy: Parent Transcript Factor -> Intermediate Transcript Factor -> Target Gene

ENO1 Multi-Layer Regulatory Cascade

Hierarchy: Parent Transcript Factor -> Intermediate Transcript Factor -> Target Gene

C).

NONO Multi-Layer Regulatory Cascade

Hierarchy: Parent Transcript Factor -> Intermediate Transcript Factor -> Target Gene

Figure 4. Multi-layer regulatory cascades surrounding the RAN-ENO1-NONO core. Gene regulatory networks reconstructed from BARNO-derived regulatory interactions reveal hierarchical transcriptional cascades centered on the core regulators RAN, ENO1, and NONO. **A).** RAN-centered regulatory cascade. **B).** ENO1-centered regulatory cascade. **C).** NONO-centered regulatory cascade.

Method

Data acquisition

Single-cell RNA sequencing data were obtained from the Broad Institute Single Cell Portal under accession SCP109. The dataset integrates melanoma transcriptomic profiles and associated clinical annotations derived from the TCGA-SKCM cohort and publicly available immunotherapy datasets.

Preprocessing of single-cell transcriptomic data

Single-cell transcriptomic data were first subjected to high-variance gene selection using a LOESS-based variance modeling approach. Genes with significant residual variance ($p < 0.2$) were retained as highly variable genes [14]. To focus on regulatory signals, the resulting gene set was intersected with transcription factors annotated in the motif database from RcisTarget [12], yielding 1234 transcription factors in the melanoma dataset.

To mitigate sparsity inherent to single-cell transcriptomic data, k-nearest neighbor (kNN) imputation was performed with $k=5$. Cell similarity was calculated using Euclidean distance [15]:

$$d(p, q) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (p_i - q_i)^2}$$

where p_i and q_i represent the expression levels of gene i in cells p and q , respectively. The imputation procedure substantially reduced the number of zero-expression entries in the expression matrix.

Finally, min-max normalization was applied to scale gene expression values to the range $[0,1]$:

$$x' = \frac{x - \min(X)}{\max(X) - \min(X)}$$

This normalization step ensured comparable feature scales for subsequent regulatory network inference and penalty calculations.

Gene regulatory network inference

Gene regulatory networks were inferred using the GENIE3 algorithm. GENIE3 employs a tree-based ensemble approach to estimate regulatory interactions between transcription factors and their potential target genes [16]. In this framework, transcription factors were treated as candidate regulators, while all remaining genes were considered potential targets.

For each dataset, GENIE3 was executed with the following parameters: $nTree = 1000$ for the melanoma dataset and $nTree = 500$ for both the CD8 and CD4 datasets. The algorithm outputs a weighted regulatory network in which each edge represents the predicted influence of a transcription factor on a target gene. The resulting weight matrix was used as the initial regulatory interaction matrix for downstream BARNO penalty calculation and module construction.

BARNO penalty calculation

To quantify the spatial dispersion of transcription factor-expressing cells in the PCA space, we defined a normalized dispersion score based on the mean squared Euclidean distance from the centroid of the cellular distribution. For a given set of cells, the dispersion was computed as the average squared distance between each cell and the global centroid. The relative dispersion (Portion) was then defined as the ratio between the dispersion of the selected cells and the dispersion of all cells:

$$Portion = \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|x_i - \mu\|^2}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \|x_i - \mu\|^2}$$

where x_i represents the PCA coordinates of cell i , μ denotes the centroid of the full cell population, n is the number of cells expressing the transcription factor, and N is the total number of cells.

To quantify the extent of batch-associated transcriptional patterns, we defined a batch penalty score based on the spatial dispersion metric described above. First, the dispersion ratio (Portion) was calculated as the normalized mean squared Euclidean distance of transcription factor-expressing cells relative to the global cellular dispersion in PCA space.

To increase sensitivity to highly dispersed transcription factor patterns, the Portion value was amplified by applying a cubic transformation. The batch penalty score was then calculated as:

$$Batch\ Penalty = \left(\frac{Portion^3}{\tau} \right)^2$$

where τ represents a predefined threshold (default $\tau = 0.5$). The cubic transformation emphasizes transcription factors with strong spatial dispersion, while the subsequent squaring step further enlarges differences among high-dispersion signals. Consequently, transcription factors whose expression patterns are strongly associated with localized or batch-specific clusters receive substantially higher penalty scores. This penalty design allows BARNO to suppress regulators whose expression patterns deviate strongly from the global biological structure.

Regulatory Weight Algorithmic Framework

To quantify transcriptional regulatory relationships between transcription factors and their target genes, we designed a regulatory weight framework that integrates regulatory strength, expression correlation, and temporal consistency. Two alternative formulations were developed: Scoring Regulatory Weight (SR Weight) and Time Regulatory Weight (TR Weight). Due to batch effects present in the datasets analyzed in this study, only the SR formulation was used for downstream analyses, while the time-based formulation is provided as an alternative framework for datasets with clear developmental trajectories.

Scoring Regulatory Weight (SR Weight)

The SR weight quantifies the regulatory strength between transcription factor i and target gene j by integrating three components: GENIE3-derived regulatory importance, expression correlation, and temporal consistency derived from Seurat scoring [17].

$$SR\ Weight_{i,j} = \Delta(GenieW_{i,j} \times R_{i,j} \times e^{-\alpha\Delta S_{i,j}}) \times Batch\ Penalty$$

where:

- $GenieW_{i,j}$ denotes the regulatory importance score inferred by the GENIE3 algorithm between transcription factor i and target gene j .
- $R_{i,j}$ represents the Pearson correlation coefficient between the transcription factor and the target gene, capturing the direction (positive or negative) of the regulatory relationship.
- $\Delta S_{i,j}$ represents the difference in Seurat-derived activity scores between the treated and untreated groups.
- α is a scaling parameter controlling the strength of temporal penalization ($\alpha = 0.5$).
- $Batch\ Penalty$ denotes the batch-associated penalty term described above.
- The exponential term $e^{-\alpha\Delta S_{i,j}}$ acts as a soft penalization mechanism, reducing the regulatory weight when the temporal ordering between transcription factor and target gene expression deviates from the expected biological pattern.
- Δ represents $treated - untreated$.

Seurat score-based temporal estimation

In biological systems, transcription factor activation typically precedes the peak expression of its downstream target genes [11]. To capture this regulatory ordering, we used Seurat module scoring to estimate transcriptional activity at the cellular level [17].

Seurat scoring assigns each cell a gene set activity score defined as the difference between the mean expression of the gene set of interest and the mean expression of a matched background gene set [17].

Compared with raw gene expression, this scoring approach reduces noise and technical variability.

To translate cell-level activity scores into gene-level temporal information, a LOESS regression was fitted between the Seurat score and the expression level of each gene [14]. The position of the maximum of the fitted curve was used to estimate the pseudo-temporal peak of gene expression. The difference between transcription factor and target gene peak positions defines $\Delta S_{i,j}$.

Because $\Delta S_{i,j}$ may vary across a wide range, directly multiplying this term could dominate the regulatory weight calculation. Therefore, we incorporated it through an exponential decay function $e^{-\alpha \Delta S_{i,j}}$, which acts as a soft penalty while preserving the influence of the GENIE3 importance and correlation terms.

In this study, we focused on transcriptional differences between treated and untreated samples. Therefore, the outer difference operator Δ was defined as the treated-untreated contrast to amplify treatment-associated regulatory signals.

Time Regulatory Weight (TR Weight)

For datasets containing clear developmental trajectories or transient cell states, we additionally defined a pseudo-time-based regulatory weight:

$$TR\ Weight_{i,j} = \Delta(GenieW_{i,j} \times R_{i,j} \times e^{\alpha \Delta T_{i,j}})$$

where $\Delta T_{i,j}$ represents the difference between the pseudo-time peak of the transcription factor and that of the target gene. Pseudo-time ordering was estimated using Slingshot, and peak positions were again determined through LOESS regression.

This formulation allows regulatory interactions to be evaluated within dynamic cellular trajectories, capturing transient regulatory programs that may occur during short-lived differentiation or transition states.

Graph Distance Calculation

In the regulatory tree construction step, edges are selected based on minimum graph distance rather than maximum regulatory weight. Therefore, regulatory weights were transformed into distances prior to tree construction.

Because regulatory weights may take both positive and negative values, the absolute value of the regulatory weight was used to represent interaction strength independent of direction. Distances were then defined as the inverse of the regulatory weight magnitude:

$$Distance_{i,j} = \frac{1}{|SR\ Weight_{i,j}| + \varepsilon}$$

or

$$Distance_{i,j} = \frac{1}{|TR\ Weight_{i,j}| + \varepsilon}$$

where $SR\ Weight_{i,j}$ and $TR\ Weight_{i,j}$ represent the scoring-based and pseudo-time-based regulatory weights between transcription factor i and target gene j , respectively. The constant ε was set to 1×10^{-6} to prevent numerical instability when the regulatory weight approaches zero.

This transformation ensures that regulatory interactions with stronger weights correspond to shorter graph distances, allowing the subsequent tree construction algorithm to preferentially retain biologically stronger regulatory relationships.

Regulatory module construction

To construct regulatory modules, transcription factors were ranked according to their regulatory weights derived from the BARNO framework. For each module, transcription factors with the strongest positive and negative regulatory weights were considered as candidate regulators.

To determine an appropriate module size, we evaluated several thresholds, including the top 20, top 15, top 10, and top 5 transcription factors ranked by regulatory weight. For each threshold, downstream survival analyses and regulatory module stability were examined.

We observed that selecting the top 15 transcription factors provided the most stable results across datasets and modules, balancing signal robustness and model interpretability. Therefore, the top 15 positively and negatively weighted transcription factors were used to define regulatory modules in subsequent analyses.

Survival Analysis and Clinical Validation

Associations between regulatory modules and patient survival were evaluated using Cox proportional hazards regression [18]. For each module, the module score was used as the predictor variable, and overall survival was used as the outcome variable. Modules with hazard ratios (HR) greater than 1.5 were considered death-associated regulatory modules and were selected for further analysis.

Kaplan-Meier survival curves were then generated to visualize survival stratification between high and low module score groups. Survival differences between groups were assessed using the log-rank test [19]. To account for multiple hypothesis testing, p-values were adjusted using the Benjamini-Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) correction [20]. Modules with FDR-adjusted p-values below the significance threshold were considered statistically significant.

Clinical survival data used in this study were obtained from the melanoma cohort included in the SCP109 dataset, which integrates clinical annotations derived from the TCGA-SKCM cohort and publicly available immunotherapy datasets.

Module reduction and core regulator identification

To identify a minimal regulatory core underlying the survival-associated modules, we performed a module reduction procedure focusing on the most death-related regulatory modules identified by Cox regression analysis. Transcription factors from these modules were first ranked according to their BARNO regulatory weights.

We then examined transcription factors that appeared repeatedly across the top death-associated modules. Regulators shared among multiple modules were considered candidate core regulators, as their recurrent presence suggests coordinated regulatory activity underlying multiple survival-associated transcriptional programs.

Based on this overlap analysis, transcription factors that consistently appeared across the selected modules were retained as core regulators for subsequent survival stratification and regulatory cascade reconstruction.

Reconstruction of multi-layer regulatory cascades

To investigate hierarchical regulatory relationships surrounding key transcription factors, we reconstructed multi-layer gene regulatory cascades based on the regulatory weights calculated by the BARNO framework. Because the regulatory weight incorporates transcriptional correlation and temporal consistency, it has the potential to capture biologically meaningful regulatory relationships between transcription factors and their target genes.

Unlike conventional approaches that construct minimum spanning trees (MSTs) to eliminate cycles, we intentionally allowed regulatory loops in order to preserve potential biological feedback relationships commonly observed in transcriptional regulatory networks.

The cascade reconstruction procedure was performed as follows:

- First, for a transcription factor of interest (parent node), the first regulatory layer was constructed by selecting the top nodes ($n = 10$) with the smallest graph distances to the parent node.
- Second, each node in the first layer was examined. If a node represented a transcription factor, its downstream targets were identified by selecting genes with the smallest graph distances to that node. These genes were added as intermediate nodes in the next regulatory layer.

This procedure was iteratively repeated until all terminal nodes corresponded to non-transcription factor genes, forming the leaf nodes of the cascade.

During this process, edges that returned to previously visited nodes, including edges pointing back to the parent transcription factor, were retained rather than removed. Although the regulatory weight calculation already penalizes inconsistent temporal and correlation relationships through the $\Delta S_{i,j}$ and $\Delta R_{i,j}$ terms, persistent loops after these penalties may represent genuine biological feedback regulation.

This approach therefore enables the reconstruction of multi-layer regulatory cascades while preserving potential feedback structures inherent to transcriptional regulatory networks.

Methodological considerations

During the development of the BARNO framework, several alternative strategies were evaluated. Pseudo-time-based regulatory weighting using Slingshot was initially considered [21-24]. However, strong batch effects were observed in the dataset, which led pseudo-time inference to primarily reflect patient-specific variation rather than true biological trajectories. As a result, pseudo-time information was excluded from the final regulatory weight calculation, although this functionality remains available in the software package for datasets with well-defined developmental trajectories.

We also evaluated integration-based approaches for regulatory signal estimation. However, integration methods tend to emphasize global expression patterns, which may obscure gene-specific regulatory timing relationships. In contrast, the peak-based strategy adopted in BARNO explicitly models the expected biological ordering in which transcription factor activation precedes the peak expression of downstream target genes, thereby reducing potential false positive regulatory relationships.

Software Implementation

All analyses were performed in the R statistical computing environment. The following R packages were used for data processing, regulatory network inference, visualization, and survival analysis: BiocManager, slingshot, RcisTarget, umap, Seurat, GENIE3, igraph, survival, survminer, ggplot2, and reshape2.

BiocManager was used for package management and installation of Bioconductor dependencies. Gene regulatory network inference was performed using GENIE3 [16], while graph-based regulatory cascade reconstruction was implemented using igraph. Pseudo-time analysis was conducted using slingshot [21-24]. Transcription factor annotations were obtained from RcisTarget [11]. Dimensionality reduction and module scoring were performed using Seurat [17] and umap [25]. Survival analyses were conducted using the survival and survminer packages. Visualization of results was generated using ggplot2, and data reshaping was performed using reshape2.

All analyses were performed using R version 4.5.2.

Software Availability

The BARNO framework is implemented as an R package and the source code is available at:

<https://github.com/yourname/BARNO>

The package provides functions for regulatory network inference, batch-aware penalization, and visualization of regulatory cascades.

Discussion

Understanding transcriptional regulatory programs that drive melanoma progression remains a major challenge in single-cell transcriptomic analysis [6,7]. In this study, we developed BARNO, a regulatory weighting framework designed to identify biologically meaningful transcription factor-target gene relationships while suppressing batch-driven transcriptional signals. By integrating regulatory importance from GENIE3 [16], expression correlation, temporal ordering inferred from transcriptional scoring, and a batch penalty mechanism, BARNO enables the construction of regulatory modules that reflect coherent biological programs rather than technical artifacts.

Using this framework, we identified several survival-associated regulatory modules in melanoma. Among them, transcription factors RAN, ENO1, and NONO consistently appeared across multiple death-associated modules. Module reduction analysis further revealed that these regulators form a minimal regulatory core capable of stratifying patient survival. Kaplan-Meier analysis demonstrated that the combined RAN-ENO1-NONO signature exhibits stronger prognostic power than individual modules, suggesting that these transcription factors may participate in coordinated transcriptional programs associated with melanoma progression.

Interestingly, several of the identified regulators have previously been implicated in cancer-related processes. ENO1 has been reported to participate in tumor metabolism and glycolytic regulation, which are frequently associated with aggressive tumor phenotypes [26,27]. NONO, a nuclear RNA-binding protein, is known to regulate transcriptional and post-transcriptional processes and has been implicated in oncogenic transcriptional programs [28]. RAN, a small GTPase involved in nucleocytoplasmic transport, has also been associated with tumor progression and mitotic regulation [29]. Although the precise role of the RAN-ENO1-

NONO regulatory axis in melanoma remains to be fully elucidated, their recurrent appearance across survival-associated modules suggests that they may participate in coordinated regulatory programs relevant to melanoma progression.

Beyond survival associations, reconstruction of multi-layer regulatory cascades revealed that the RAN-ENO1-NONO core is embedded within hierarchical regulatory networks involving multiple intermediate transcription factors and downstream target genes. Importantly, the regulatory cascades reconstructed by BARNO preserve feedback loops rather than enforcing tree-like structures. Such feedback regulation is common in transcriptional networks and may play important roles in maintaining regulatory stability or enabling adaptive responses during tumor evolution [30,31]. The presence of partially overlapping regulatory cascades suggests that the identified transcription factors may act as coordinated regulatory hubs rather than isolated regulators.

A key methodological contribution of this study lies in the design of the BARNO regulatory weighting scheme. Many regulatory inference approaches rely primarily on correlation or feature importance scores, which may be strongly influenced by batch effects or highly expressed genes [7,17,21]. By incorporating spatial dispersion penalties and temporal consistency constraints, BARNO aims to reduce regulatory relationships that arise from technical artifacts while preserving interactions consistent with biological regulatory ordering. The peak-based temporal estimation used in this framework reflects the biological expectation that transcription factor activation typically precedes the expression peak of downstream target genes [30]. This strategy reduces the likelihood of identifying spurious regulatory relationships that violate expected transcriptional timing.

Despite these promising results, several limitations should be noted. First, the current analysis was conducted using a melanoma dataset derived from the SCP109 study, and validation across additional independent cohorts would strengthen the robustness of the identified regulatory modules. Second, the regulatory cascades inferred in this study are computational predictions based on transcriptomic data and require experimental validation to confirm the underlying molecular mechanisms. Finally, while the BARNO framework attempts to reduce batch-associated transcriptional signals, residual batch effects may still influence regulatory inference in highly heterogeneous datasets.

Future studies may extend the BARNO framework to integrate additional data modalities, such as chromatin accessibility or proteomic measurements, to further refine regulatory inference. In the context of melanoma, investigating whether the identified RAN-ENO1-NONO regulatory core contributes to treatment resistance or tumor-immune interactions may provide insights into mechanisms underlying melanoma progression. More broadly, the BARNO framework may provide a general strategy for identifying biologically meaningful regulatory programs in single-cell datasets affected by technical heterogeneity.

Conclusions

To capture biologically meaningful transcription factor-target gene relationships while reducing batch-driven transcriptional signals in single-cell transcriptomic data, we developed BARNO. By integrating regulatory importance, expression correlation, temporal consistency, and batch-aware penalization, BARNO enables the construction of regulatory modules that better reflect underlying biological programs.

Applying this framework to melanoma single-cell datasets, we identified several survival-associated regulatory modules and further uncovered a minimal regulatory core consisting of RAN, ENO1, and NONO. Module reduction and survival analyses demonstrated that this transcriptional core provides strong prognostic stratification, while reconstruction of multi-layer regulatory cascades revealed hierarchical regulatory relationships surrounding these transcription factors.

Together, these findings suggest that BARNO provides a useful computational strategy for uncovering biologically coherent regulatory programs in heterogeneous single-cell datasets. The framework may facilitate the identification of clinically relevant regulatory signatures and provide insights into transcriptional mechanisms underlying melanoma progression.

Declarations

Consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

All datasets analyzed in this study are publicly available. The melanoma single-cell dataset, including immunotherapy (ICB) and TCGA melanoma data, were obtained from the SCP109 resource, originally reported by Livnat et al. (2018). Detailed accession information can be found in the original publication: https://singlecell.broadinstitute.org/single_cell/study/SCP109/melanoma-immunotherapy-resistance. The BARNO framework is implemented as an open-source R package and is available at: <https://github.com/xxxxxi0001/BARNO>. An archived version of the software is available at Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19058450>.

Competing interests

The author declares that there are no competing interests.

Author contributions

XZ conceived and designed the study, developed the BARNO framework, implemented the computational pipeline and R package, performed all analyses, generated the figures, and wrote the manuscript. The author read and approved the final manuscript.

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Supplementary

Supplementary Figure S1. Visualization of sample distribution, treatment status, and NEUROD1 expression in melanoma single-cell transcriptomic data. UMAP projections of melanoma cells colored by **a)** patient sample identity, **b)** treatment condition (treated vs. untreated), and **c)** expression level of NEUROD1. The sample-colored UMAP reveals strong patient-specific clustering, indicating substantial batch-associated variation across samples. Although NEUROD1 appeared as a high-weight transcription factor in the initial GENIE3 inference, its expression pattern largely overlaps with sample-specific clusters rather than biologically coherent cell populations, suggesting that its high regulatory weight may be driven by batch-associated signals rather than true regulatory relevance

A).

B).

Supplementary Figure S2. Survival analysis of candidate transcription factors and combinations of the RAN-ENO1-NONO regulatory core. Kaplan-Meier survival curves illustrating the association between transcription factor expression and patient survival. **A).** Survival curves for the top 10 transcription factors identified from survival-associated regulatory modules. **B).** Survival curves for pairwise combinations of the core regulators RAN, ENO1, and NONO.

Supplementary Figure S3. Validation of the RAN-ENO1-NONO regulatory signature in an independent anti-CTLA-4 immunotherapy cohort. Kaplan-Meier survival analysis evaluating the prognostic value of the RAN-ENO1-NONO transcriptional signature in patients treated with anti-CTLA-4 immunotherapy (aCTLA4 cohort).

Cell Type	Gene List
Th1	"IFNG", "CXCR3", "STAT4", "IL12RB2", "TBX21", "TNF", "IL2"
Tfh	"CXCR5", "ICOS", "PDCD1", "IL21", "BCL6"
Effector Memory CD4 T	"CD4", "ANXA1", "IL7R", "S100A4", "PRDM1"
Treg	"FOXP3", "IL2RA", "IKZF2", "CTLA4", "TNFRSF4", "TNFRSF18", "IL10"

Supplementary Table S1. CD4 Gene List selected for Seurat scoring.

Cell Type	Gene List
Activated cytotoxic CD8	"GZMB", "PRF1", "IFNG", "CD69", "HLA-DRA", "EOMES", "RUNX3", "NKG7", "GZMA"
Exhausted CD8	"PDCD1", "LAG3", "HAVCR2", "TIGIT", "CTLA4", "ENTPD1", "TOX", "PRDM1"

Supplementary Table S2. CD8 Gene List selected for Seurat scoring.

Cell Type	Gene List
MITF-high differentiated melanoma (Melanocytic)	"TYR", "DCT", "MLANA", "PMEL", "MITF", "SOX10", "MIA", "GPNMB", "S100B", "ERBB3"
Melanoma invasive	"AXL", "NGFR", "WNT5A", "ZEB1", "TWIST1", "PDGFRB", "VIM", "SERPINE"
Stress-Like melanoma	"HSPA1A", "HSP90AA1", "ATF3", "DDIT3", "JUN", "FOS", "ATF4"
Highly-proliferate melanoma	"MKI67", "TOP2A", "PCNA", "CDK1", "CENPF"

Supplementary Table S3. Melanoma Gene List selected for Seurat scoring.

Transcript Factor (Treg)	Calculated Weight (Treg)	Transcript Factor (Treg)	Calculated Weight (Treg)
FOSL2	817.8844	ZSCAN16	-1147.85
IRF2	714.6267	HMG20B	-991.6955
PQBP1	693.4973	NME1	-927.6668
ZNF800	639.2422	NCALD	-861.9313
TAF6	628.2635	IL21	-830.1915
ZNF581	623.2473	RFXANK	-807.4244
ZNF3	587.4468	RELA	-783.542
RAN	582.2066	CERS2	-762.1252
YY1	575.819	TRMT1	-748.6213
DIDO1	565.0012	PML	-715.8249

Supplementary Table S4. Regulatory CD4 T top 10 candidates

Transcript Factor (Th1)	Calculated Weight (Th1)	Transcript Factor (Th1)	Calculated Weight (Th1)
ZBTB32	873.9369	IRF5	-2020.488
ZNF3	808.8239	HMG20B	-1962.358
ZSCAN32	800.4599	IL21	-1941.653
ZNF671	780.8951	ZSCAN16	-1859.035
ZNF708	772.0026	NME1	-1757.932
ZNF211	747.8454	ZBED2	-1673.617
ZNF506	742.2106	RFXANK	-1649.652
ZNF33A	736.2045	NCALD	-1636.422

HSF2	730.8666	VPS72	-1297.171
ZBTB25	719.0645	ILF2	-1235.366

Supplementary Table S5. Helper CD4 T1 top 10 candidates

Transcript Factor (Tfh)	Calculated Weight (Tfh)	Transcript Factor (Tfh)	Calculated Weight (Tfh)
ZSCAN16	1350.5131	BHLHE40	-1314.6139
NME1	905.2479	FOSL2	-1216.9627
HMG20B	867.3668	ZBTB32	-1195.5066
RELA	826.0226	ETV7	-1152.4078
TCF7	804.2836	ENO1	-1012.7527
ATF2	785.5547	ZBED2	-1006.173
ZBTB8A	785.2209	CREB3	-860.7184
DRAP1	778.347	TGIF1	-851.4908
ZKSCAN3	745.1631	PRDM1	-811.2393
RFXANK	740.0867	NR4A3	-810.6205

Supplementary Table S6. Follicular CD4 T top 10 candidates

Transcript Factor (EMT)	Calculated Weight (EMT)	Transcript Factor (EMT)	Calculated Weight (EMT)
ZBTB32	1391.7592	IRF5	-2692.5775
ETV7	1098.8615	ZSCAN16	-2544.8838
ZNF383	869.0498	ETV7	-2340.158
ZNF562	817.3587	NME1	-2149.1033
JUNB	783.7084	IL21	-2120.6058
PPARD	780.9193	NCALD	-1971.6121
ZSCAN26	773.4447	HMG20B	-1961.4686
ZNF32	755.4691	BATF	-1954.0151
ZNF506	741.7846	ZBED2	-1910.5038
KLF10	714.9523	CERS2	-1578.4613

Supplementary Table S7. Effector Memory CD4 T top 10 candidates

Transcript Factor (Cytotoxic)	Calculated Weight (Cytotoxic)	Transcript Factor (Cytotoxic)	Calculated Weight (Cytotoxic)
ZNF227	1227.1983	GTF2A2	-1344.271
MED30	967.8503	RAN	-1130.7988
USF1	962.1901	ZBTB17	-1011.9599
ZNF234	881.8387	ZNF706	-1004.8964
TRIM28	880.9578	PINX1	-990.4908
RLF	874.6692	ZNF134	-952.3533
FOXP3	872.6753	IRF3	-947.1072
ZNF302	866.123	ZNF700	-942.1348
ATF6	860.0777	ZNF586	-930.0358
CHD1	837.194	ZNF830	-921.1333

Supplementary Table S8. Cytotoxic CD8 T top 10 candidates

Transcript Factor (Exhausted)	Calculated Weight (Exhausted)	Transcript Factor (Exhausted)	Calculated Weight (Exhausted)
ARGFX	1284.9772	ZNF511	-1563.9467
POU5F1	1233.7108	GTF2A2	-1460.8957
CRX	1219.0714	BAD	-1232.1448
ZNF483	1154.7434	USF1	-1197.6469
ZFP14	1141.0958	ZNF121	-1190.0794
SHOX	1138.9421	ACAA1	-1169.0468
ZNF234	1086.1044	ZNF689	-1164.6622
GATAD1	1081.1238	ZNF184	-1159.3015
ZNF490	1079.2668	IRF3	-1144.4746
JUN	1068.342	ENO1	-1107.106

Supplementary Table S9. Exhausted CD8 T top 10 candidates

Transcript Factor (Melanocytic)	Calculated Weight (Melanocytic)	Transcript Factor (Melanocytic)	Calculated Weight (Melanocytic)
RAN	512.9117	ENO1	-1063.0678
DLX5	473.6931	RAN	-819.7409
EZH2	471.5713	ATF4	-723.8965
CTCF	451.1096	PIR	-712.8565
NME1	449.0312	NONO	-706.07
ILF2	410.221	GTF3A	-614.2613
ILF3	410.0117	RNF114	-568.9876
MSC	403.1989	CTNNA1	-564.0996
PARP1	398.5517	NME1	-551.8389
ID2	397.6322	SP100	-549.4004

Supplementary Table S10. Melanocytic top 10 candidates

Transcript Factor (Stress Melanoma)	Calculated Weight (Stress Melanoma)	Transcript Factor (Stress Melanoma)	Calculated Weight (Stress Melanoma)
RAN	1235.2969	RAN	-944.2255
NME1	1043.5212	MITF	-785.9896
ILF2	809.4663	ENO1	-763.1351
ENO1	805.9324	PIR	-684.3625
NONO	798.7677	NONO	-643.6016
APEX1	689.9946	SNAI2	-571.4376
PARP1	671.9388	IRF7	-553.5352
EZH2	604.242	NME1	-527.0916
DLX5	560.6701	ZNF706	-501.3833
CTCF	556.6849	STAT1	-496.4607

Supplementary Table S11. Stress Melanoma top 10 candidates

Transcript Factor (Proliferate Melanoma)	Calculated Weight (Proliferate Melanoma)	Transcript Factor (Proliferate Melanoma)	Calculated Weight (Proliferate Melanoma)
ENO1	834.4115	RAN	-1098.9689
PIR	732.2295	ENO1	-928.0351
RAN	693.6529	NONO	-856.8979
MITF	633.4716	ILF2	-855.0932
NONO	632.2133	NME1	-831.8608
SNAI2	586.6733	PARP1	-704.6684
PAX3	509.0465	APEX1	-681.1303
NME1	505.7065	ILF3	-612.9898
GTF3A	492.2936	DLX5	-563.9869
ZNF706	477.5048	ZNF207	-553.0691

Supplementary Table S12. Proliferate Melanoma top 10 candidates

Transcript Factor (Invasive Melanoma)	Calculated Weight (Invasive Melanoma)	Transcript Factor (Invasive Melanoma)	Calculated Weight (Invasive Melanoma)
RAN	660.0321	PIR	-908.0041
NME1	539.5408	ENO1	-807.289
ILF3	523.7601	MITF	-798.4934
NONO	511.7188	RAN	-578.5073
CTCF	508.7142	GTF3A	-577.3877
ENO1	506.3072	SNAI2	-569.6826
HMGA1	481.1666	PAX3	-560.5793
ILF2	461.2113	CTNNB1	-536.1966
DLX5	456.2056	ZNF706	-528.9596
ZNF207	433.0538	ETV5	-526.2106

Supplementary Table S13. Invasive Melanoma top 20 candidates

Module (Top 10)	Coefficient	HR	z-score	p-value	Lower95	Upper95	FDR	Direction
TEMemory positive	-0.5661478	0.56770815	-4.0475359	5.18E-05	0.43158226	0.74676968	0.00103519	pro-survival
Proliferate melanoma neg	0.65842015	1.93173807	3.33701535	0.00084683	1.31219773	2.84378787	0.00846833	pro-death
Th1 positive	-0.4575388	0.63283927	-3.1758513	0.00149398	0.47715825	0.83931386	0.00995983	pro-survival
Tfh neg	-0.2664183	0.76611856	-3.0871784	0.00202066	0.64690233	0.9073049	0.01010331	pro-survival
Proliferate melanoma pos	0.36172383	1.43580236	2.79367183	0.00521133	1.1139901	1.85058055	0.02084533	pro-death
TEMemory neg	-0.2137997	0.8075101	-2.6712222	0.00755756	0.69027056	0.94466227	0.02519186	pro-survival
Invasive melanoma neg	0.2990238	1.34854172	2.42989967	0.015103	1.05953523	1.7163797	0.04315144	pro-death
Exhausted pos	-0.4847009	0.61588139	-2.2571917	0.0239961	0.40430885	0.93816863	0.05999025	pro-survival
Cytotoxic pos	-0.4133614	0.66142321	-2.1934764	0.02827307	0.45716209	0.9569487	0.06282905	pro-survival
Stress melanoma pos	0.27532033	1.31695246	1.90796191	0.05639614	0.99252415	1.7474273	0.10466016	pro-death
Invasive melanoma pos	0.27880012	1.32154317	1.89901057	0.05756309	0.99109115	1.76217532	0.10466016	pro-death
Melanocytic pos	0.27822986	1.32078976	1.81106864	0.07013023	0.97738522	1.78484955	0.11688371	pro-death

Melanocytic neg	0.36244243	1.43683449	1.67537151	0.09386136	0.9402895	2.19559334	0.1444021	pro-death
Treg negative	0.3068605	1.35915135	1.42275248	0.15480792	0.89059434	2.07422427	0.22115417	pro-death
Th1 negative	-0.2080222	0.81218898	-1.3636772	0.17266918	0.60229672	1.09522586	0.23022558	pro-survival
Cytotoxic negative	-0.3950895	0.67361975	-1.2217129	0.22181623	0.35739206	1.26965205	0.27727029	pro-survival
Stress melanoma neg	0.1019131	1.10728724	0.76555663	0.44394016	0.85299385	1.43739023	0.52228254	pro-death
Tfh positive	-0.1057055	0.8996896	-0.3775863	0.70573794	0.51975469	1.55735269	0.78415327	pro-survival
Treg positive	0.06448579	1.06661042	0.15685966	0.87535546	0.47651067	2.38747601	0.89107974	pro-death
Exhausted negative	-0.0464602	0.95460253	-0.1369381	0.89107974	0.49093918	1.85616878	0.89107974	pro-survival

Supplementary Table 14. Top 10 TF cox single run result in total

Module (Top 5)	Coefficient	HR	z-score	p-value	Lower95	Upper95	FDR	Direction
TEMemory positive	-0.4735131	0.62281045	-5.0421005	4.60E-07	0.51810522	0.74867584	9.21E-06	pro-survival
TEMemory negative	-0.364229	0.69473206	-3.8433659	0.00012136	0.57696632	0.83653519	0.00121358	pro-survival
Th1 positive	-0.3555592	0.70078145	-3.3754885	0.00073685	0.57006023	0.86147851	0.00311215	pro-survival
Proliferate melanoma neg	0.67005459	1.95434401	3.3604921	0.00077804	1.3221429	2.8888409	0.00311215	pro-death
Stress melanoma pos	0.67005459	1.95434401	3.3604921	0.00077804	1.3221429	2.8888409	0.00311215	pro-death
Melanocytic neg	0.48367062	1.62201729	3.29671353	0.00097823	1.21667106	2.1624087	0.00326077	pro-death
Tfh neg	-0.2473001	0.78090627	-2.9057099	0.00366421	0.66092862	0.92266333	0.00833648	pro-survival
Stress melanoma neg	0.31659974	1.37245312	2.89834158	0.00375142	1.10794116	1.70011517	0.00833648	pro-death
Proliferate melanoma pos	0.31659974	1.37245312	2.89834158	0.00375142	1.10794116	1.70011517	0.00833648	pro-death
Invasive melanoma neg	0.26516547	1.30364667	2.48327846	0.01301793	1.05747049	1.60713198	0.02603586	pro-death
Cytotoxic positive	-0.3785872	0.68482827	-1.9554532	0.05052961	0.46858036	1.00087371	0.09187201	pro-survival
Treg neg	0.30359752	1.35472369	1.8643616	0.06227094	0.98455241	1.86407169	0.1037849	pro-death
Cytotoxic neg	0.4161591	1.51612706	1.80525963	0.07103406	0.96496508	2.38209786	0.10848688	pro-death
Exhausted pos	-0.2712276	0.76244291	-1.7747401	0.07594082	0.56509443	1.02871161	0.10848688	pro-survival
Th1 neg	-0.2861441	0.75115436	-1.6093481	0.10754024	0.53013258	1.06432409	0.14338699	pro-survival
Melanocytic pos	0.10562526	1.11140531	1.169383	0.24224936	0.93108032	1.32665435	0.29079971	pro-death
Invasive melanoma pos	0.14121695	1.15167448	1.1572267	0.24717975	0.90668659	1.46285842	0.29079971	pro-death
Tfh pos	0.06102551	1.06292603	0.37523051	0.70748904	0.77280179	1.46196831	0.78609894	pro-death
Exhausted neg	-0.0817071	0.92154185	-0.2969665	0.76649206	0.53742305	1.58020648	0.80683374	pro-survival
Treg pos	-0.045224	0.9557834	-0.1798535	0.8572676	0.58388293	1.56456348	0.8572676	pro-survival

Supplementary Table 15. Top 5 TF cox single run result in total